

www.bjisrd.com

A Modification of RC4 Algorithm Using Irreducible Polynomials Over $GF(p^n)$

Dilshad Akhtar,

Research Associate, T.M. Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812007, Bihar, India

M. R. Hassan,

Retd. Professor, University Department of Mathematics, T.M. Bhagalpur University,
Bhagalpur-812007, Bihar, India

Abstract: *This manuscript deals with the presentation of a modification of the RC4 stream cipher. Since the existing variants of RC4 are not sufficiently secure in digital communication, the main goal of this work is to optimize security performance of PRNG. For this, we have proposed a new pseudorandom number generator based on RC4 namely RC4-IP in which we have used the multiplicative inverse of polynomials under the irreducible polynomials over $GF(7^3)$. Analyzing the security of the proposed algorithm in terms of the randomness of the output keystream bytes it was found that the proposed algorithm is more secure than the existing variants of the RC4 Stream Cipher.*

Key words: *Stream cipher, RC4, PRNG, Multiplicative inverse, Randomness.*

1. Introduction: In a digital communication system, network security and secrecy of messages are very important. Security can be provided by using cryptographic systems. The cryptographic system is divided in three categories (i) without using a key (ii) symmetric key cryptography or private key cryptography and (iii) asymmetric key cryptography or public key cryptography. For Symmetric key cryptography or private key cryptography, the same key is used in encryption and decryption. Symmetric key cipher is also classified into two categories as stream cipher and block cipher.

RC4 stream cipher is broadly used in a number of software and web applications including Wireless Equivalent Privacy (WEP), Wi-Fi Protected Access (WPA) and Secure Socket Layer (SSL) Protocols, Microsoft windows Apple OCE (Apple Open Collaboration Environment), Secure SQL (a server for database management) etc.

Ronald Rivest (1987) designed RC4 Stream Cipher for RSA data security. The key size used in RC4 stream cipher with byte-oriented operations is variable. The algorithm is based on the use of a random permutation. As RC4 is a byte-oriented stream cipher in which a 256-byte key stream is generated, it is used in a byte (8 bits) of a plaintext exclusive-ored with a byte of the key to produce a byte of cipher text. RC4 is also used in many data communication and networking protocols including SSL/TLS and the IEEE802.11 wireless LAN standard. The design simplicity of the RC4 stream cipher makes the research community always attracted towards it. To remove the weakness of randomness and related cryptanalytic attacks, different types of RC4 variants have been proposed in the literature. But the recent cryptanalytic attacks shows that in spite of a number of efforts in improving the security of RC4, weaknesses still exist in RC4 stream cipher that's why the RC4 stream cipher is still an insecure cipher. However, the design simplicity, statistical weakness and nonrandom behavior between the key leaves the key stream open to different cryptanalytic attacks.

Hammood et al (2013) proposed a new form of the RC4 stream cipher with a random initial state (RRC4) to solve the RC4's correlation problem with the public known outputs of the internal state in which RRC4 solves the weak keys problem of the RC4 using random initialization of internal state S . Experimental results showed that the output streams generated by RRC4 are more random than the generated by classical RC4. Further Maytham M. Hammood et al (2013) established a new variant of RC4 stream cipher with two state tables (RC4-2S) which solves the correlation problem with the public known output of the internal state using permutation between S_1 and S_2 . It is to be noted that the time of the key generation of the RC4-2S is faster than that of the original RC4 due to less number of operations per a key generation required by former. The final result confirmed that the output streams generated by the RC4-2S are more random than that generated by RC4 while requiring less time than RC4.

Poonam Jindal et al (2015) summarized the various weaknesses of the RC4 algorithm followed by recent improvements available in the literature. Author's chronological survey corroborates the fact that even though researchers are working on the RC4 streams cipher since the last two decades but it still offers a plethora of research issues.

J K M Sadique Uz Zaman et al (2016) established a new pseudorandom number generator GF7 in which the multiplicative inverses of all non-zero elemental polynomials under all irreducible polynomials over $GF(p^n)$ are used as initial seeds and the rest part of GF7 algorithm is identical to the RC4 algorithm. Both the S-box and K-box of GF7 depend upon the irreducible polynomial so keeping the irreducible polynomial secret between the sender and the receiver and hence the security of the series of output sequences will be increased.

Isnar Sumartono et al (2016) overviewed the RC4 algorithm in which keys are generated by forming the S-box. The result of the S-box is xored with the existing plaintext.

Poonam Jindal and Brahmjit Singh et al (2016) investigated different types of vulnerabilities in the RC4 and its variants to defeat security attacks. They developed three variants of RC4 known as RC4-M1, RC4-M2, and RC4-M3. The security of the proposed schemes was analyzed in terms of randomness and computational complexity. All three proposed variants qualify the NIST statistical test suit of randomness satisfactorily but offered computational complexity in terms of greater number of operations relative to the existing variants. The strength of these schemes had been analyzed against different cryptanalytic attempts and shown the resistance of proposed schemes against adversary. The security performance tradeoff had been analyzed in terms of run time, CPU cycles consumed and energy cost.

Suman Das et al (2019) claimed that, in RC4 stream cipher, the swap function is responsible for essential biases in the output. By analyzing different variants of RC4, the authors have attempted to make their work more secured by discarding initial bytes and if so, what is the optimum limit. Also multiple S-boxes are generated by different logics and a unique key-mixing procedure has been implemented to make KRC4 more robust.

M A Budiman et al (2019) described the RC4+ algorithm and the Variably Modified Permutation Composition (VMPC) algorithm in the form of stream ciphers. To achieve the security objectives, two algorithms were used and applied into the three-pass protocol schemes.

Talib M. Jawad and Dalal W. Ahmed et al (2020) proposed a new PRNG for creating random integer key sequence with the same length of the plaintext used for permuting the characters positions in the confusion stage and as an initial key for the RC4 random generator. The RC4 algorithm is used to generate other PRNG key sequence to modify the value of the characters during the diffusion stage. The experimental results proved that the proposed scheme can resist the recognized attacks like differential, statistical and brute force attacks. Also the generated sequences satisfied the statistical tests on the NIST suite.

In the present study we have proposed a new PRNG referred as RC4-IP using multiplicative inverses of elemental polynomials under the irreducible polynomials over $GF(7^3)$. The multiplicative inverse of polynomials over $GF(7^3)$ with respect to the irreducible polynomials have been found by Extended Euclidean Algorithm (EEA). A number of modifications have been carried out on improving the strength of RC4-IP algorithm.

2. Extended Euclidean Algorithm (EEA) for polynomials:

Let $a(x)$ and $b(x)$ be two polynomials then the Extended Euclidean Algorithm computes other two polynomials $p(x)$ and $q(x)$ such that $a(x)p(x) + b(x)q(x) = \gcd(a(x),b(x))$

2.1 Computation of multiplicative inverses using EEA for polynomials over a finite field $GF(p^n)$:

Let $a(x)$ be a monic irreducible polynomial and $b(x)$ be a non-zero elemental polynomial over $GF(p^n)$ then we have to find the polynomials $p(x)$ and $q(x)$ using EEA with iterations:

Initialization: Choosing, $A_1 = 1, A_2 = 0, A_3 = a(x), B_1 = 0, B_2 = 1, B_3 = b(x)$ then iterations are

$$Q \leftarrow A_3 / B_3, A_1 \leftarrow B_1, A_2 \leftarrow B_2, A_3 \leftarrow B_3$$

$$B_1 \leftarrow A_1 - Q \times B_1, B_2 \leftarrow A_2 - Q \times B_2, B_3 \leftarrow A_3 - Q \times B_3$$

Iteration Table:

	A_1	A_2	A_3	B_1	B_2	B_3
Initialization:	1	0	$a(x)$	0	1	$b(x)$
Iterations:						
$Q=A_3/B_3$	0	1	$b(x)$	$1-Q \times 0$	$0-Q \times 1$	$a(x)-Q \times b(x)$

The iterations are terminated when the remainder becomes a polynomial of degree zero (i.e, a constant). Now any non-zero element of a field is a unit of the domain of polynomials over that field so it is conventional in the case of field to divide the result of the algorithm by its leading coefficient, producing a monic polynomial of degree zero i.e, 1 which is called the greatest common divisor of the two polynomials. The gcd computed above is accordingly taken to be 1.

If $\gcd(a(x),b(x)) = 1$ then we can find the multiplicative inverse of $b(x)$ with respect to $a(x)$ given as following examples.

Example1: Let $a(x) = x^3 + 6x^2 + 4x + 1$ be a monic irreducible polynomial and $b(x) = x^2 + 1$ be an elemental polynomial over $GF(7^3)$ then to find the multiplicative inverse of $b(x)$ with respect to $a(x)$ using EEA for polynomials over finite field $GF(7^3)$.

Iteration Table:

	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃ =a(x)	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃ =b(x)
Initialization:	1	0	$x^3 + 6x^2 + 4x + 1$	0	1	$x^2 + 1$
Iteration1:						
Q = x+6	0	1	$x^2 + 1$	1	6x+1	3x+2
Iteration2:						
Q = 5x+6	1	6x+1	3x+2	2x+1	$5x^2 + x + 2$	3

Now, we terminate the iterations because in iteration 2 we got the remainder 3 i.e, a polynomial of degree zero. So by EEA (Extended Euclidean Algorithm) then there exists two polynomials such that

$$a(x) p(x) + b(x)q(x) = \text{remainder} = 3$$

$$\text{i.e, } (x^3 + 6x^2 + 4x + 1) \times (2x + 1) + (x^2 + 1) \times (5x^2 + x + 2) = 3 \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Here, 3 is a non-zero unit element of the finite field $GF(7^3)$ so we divide the result (1) of the algorithm by its leading coefficient 3 for producing a monic polynomial of degree zero, i.e, 1 is called gcd of two polynomials $a(x)$ and $b(x)$ i.e, $\gcd(a(x),b(x)) = 1$

$$\Rightarrow (x^3 + 6x^2 + 4x + 1) \times (2x + 1) \times 3^{-1} + (x^2 + 1) \times (5x^2 + x + 2) \times 3^{-1} = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow (x^3 + 6x^2 + 4x + 1) \times (2x + 1) \times 5 + (x^2 + 1) \times (5x^2 + x + 2) \times 5 = 1 \text{ [as } 3^{-1} = 5 \text{ in } GF(7) \text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow (x^2 + 1)^{-1} = 5 \times (5x^2 + x + 2) \text{ mod } (x^3 + 6x^2 + 4x + 1)$$

$$\Rightarrow (x^2 + 1)^{-1} = 4x^2 + 5x + 3$$

Example2: Let $a(x) = x^3 + 4x + 1$ be a monic irreducible polynomial and $b(x) = x^2 + 1$ be an elemental polynomial over $GF(7^3)$ then to find the multiplicative inverse of $b(x)$ with respect to $a(x)$ using EEA for polynomials over finite field $GF(7^3)$, the iteration table is as follows:

	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃ =a(x)	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃ =b(x)
Initialization:	1	0	$x^3 + 4x + 1$	0	1	$x^2 + 1$
Iteration1:						
Q = x	0	1	$x^2 + 1$	1	6x	3x+1
Iteration2:						
Q = 5x+3	1	6x	3x+1	2x+4	$5x^2 + 3x + 1$	5

Now, we terminate the iterations because in iteration 2, we got the remainder 5.

i.e, $(x^3 + 4x + 1) \times (2x + 4) + (x^2 + 1) \times (5x^2 + 3x + 1) = 5 \dots\dots\dots(2)$

Now, 5 is a non-zero unit element of the finite field $GF(7^3)$ so we divide the result (1) of the algorithm by 5 , we get,

$\Rightarrow (x^3 + 4x + 1) \times (2x + 4) \times 5^{-1} + (x^2 + 1) \times (5x^2 + 3x + 1) \times 5^{-1} = 1$

$\Rightarrow (x^3 + 4x + 1) \times (2x + 4) \times 3 + (x^2 + 1) \times (5x^2 + 3x + 1) \times 3 = 1 \dots\dots\dots(3)$

[as $5^{-1} = 3$ in $GF(7)$]

Since $\text{gcd}(a(x), b(x)) = 1$ hence the multiplicative inverse of $b(x)$ with respect to the irreducible polynomial $a(x)$ can be written as

$(x^2 + 1)^{-1} = 3 \times (5x^2 + 3x + 1) \pmod{(x^3 + 4x + 1)}$

i.e, $(x^2 + 1)^{-1} = x^2 + 2x + 3$

2.1 Table1:

001,004,005,002,003,006,613,314,352,326,246,116,402,345,123,542,443,561,201,513,251,552,132,156,603,362,143,526,634,415,104,621,645,225,432,264,506,216,334,235,654,164,305,661,531,451,425,463,423,453,330,361,043,150,436,306,140,262,434,152,530,015,554,421,431,021,236,302,130,126,224,032,622,565,611,404,111,516,414,036,520,546,400,105,342,114,241,564,644,033,566,445,411,313,060,403,642,215,025,265,460,550,253,534,444,610,643,623,242,200,053,503,461,420,650,131,046,252,406,632,521,322,442,055,124,662,153,214,501,254,450,014,633,030,226,205,244,321,545,413,636,112,344,051,202,311,631,540,125,641,612,061,110,504,266,365,163,011,426,556,532,255,233,336,606,424,013,102,410,616,560,054,543,323,422,601,151,664,263,020,655,555,462,012,452,600,430,656,446,103,035,635,510,312,615,146,660,016,165,136,652,230,331,162,465,260,142,042,604,222,121,340,100,325,065,315,355,122,050,514,113,626,106,605,454,234,023,210,161,360,245,064,353,101,441,544,522,203,221,351,066,614,412,511,562,243,524,220,310,512,052,364,466,505,026,433,665,141,144,232,456,533,502,551,040,115,063,320,523,206,563,624,301,653,022,335,455,256,145,204,525,031,646,120,350,316,333,024,500,535,154,134,160,354,341,620,034,416,440,324,211,135,304,010,464,366,332,602,044,133,213,536,663,435,666,300,231,250,041,363,261,651,303,166,212,155,045,553,223,640,45,541,056,346,356,401,062,240,625,343,515,630.

List of the total 342 multiplicative inverses of the 342 non-zero elemental polynomials with respect to the irreducible polynomial $x^3 + 6x^2 + 4x + 1$ over the finite field $GF(7^3)$.

2.3 Table2.

001,004,005,002,003,006,603,253,151,562,453,242,115,305,265,165,121,464,446,631,201,363,423,341,554,641,545,506,232,136,223,436,354,414,402,146,331,313,656,612,512,104,662,535,324,215,626,524,462,123,132,252,060,116,351,420,510,614,541,534,016,105,611,023,314,101,646,556,211,555,653,102,526,142,544,042,440,250,134,234,245,304,051,523,012,216,551,400,514,366,212,206,540,665,511,022,650,231,030,415,443,451,564,161,220,126,260,502,452,064,152,210,652,640,043,342,406,624,615,200,041,642,143,533,664,344,324,015,663,542,144,404,141,644,103,011,620,360,336,666,421,365,622,401,021,613,623,552,343,531,145,020,513,431,456,445,053,122,600,352,444,466,432,241,163,563,503,630,052,465,450,504,416,256,353,033,224,302,240,455,460,660,106,316,340,045,364,516,255,442,505,031,355,262,156,154,264,050,632,246,434,225,522,621,515,422,046,202,335,110,261,413,032,430,461,601,424,310,322,530,405,553,044,140,521,361,203,320,312,025,333,204,214,014,536,345,311,346,425,100,655,024,332,321,546,616,213,326,334,362,040,111,164,056,306,155,412,356,636,441,410,150,066,604,133,433,303,633,235,114,062,454,162,113,244,634,135,036,500,560,153,301,435,034,130,125,550,625,013,325,205,610,651,315,426,661,010,525,645,654,565,120,055,266,112,230,501,254,411,263,300,226,561,065,330,026,403,532,543,643,520,222,035,233,635,251,605,124,166,566,221,131,606,463,054,350,602,061,243,236,16
--

List of the total 342 multiplicative inverses of the 342 non-zero elemental polynomials with respect to the irreducible polynomial $x^3 + 4x + 1$ over the finite field $GF(7^3)$.

3. RC4 Stream Cipher:

RC4 is based on the concept of a state S and having two components namely the Key Scheduling Algorithm (KSA) and the Pseudorandom Generation Algorithm (PRGA). The KSA uses the key K to shuffle the elements of S and the PRGA uses this scrambled permutation to generate pseudorandom keystream bytes. Two indices i and j are used in RC4 where i is a deterministic index that is incremented by 1 (mod 256) in each step and j serves as a pseudorandom index that is updated depending on the secret key K and the state S . If the length of the key K is 256 bytes, then T is taken as K otherwise for a key of length $keylen$ bytes, the first $keylen$ elements of T are taken from K and then K is repeated as many times as necessary to fill out T . These preliminary operations can be summarized by the following initialization:

```

Input: Secret key array  $K[0,1,\dots,255]$ 
Output: Scrambled permutation array  $S[0,1,\dots,255]$ 
Initialization:
    for  $i=0,1,\dots,255$ 
         $S[i] = i$  ;
         $T[i] = K[i \bmod keylen]$  ;
Permutation of  $S$ :
     $j = 0$  ;
    for  $i = 0,1,\dots,255$ 
         $j = (j + S[i] + T[i])$  ;
        swap ( $S[i], S[j]$ ) ;

```

Algorithm: RC4 KSA

```

Input: Key-dependent scrambled permutation array  $S[0,1,\dots,255]$ .
Output: Pseudorandom keystream bytes  $Z$ .
Initialization:
     $i = j = 0$  ;
Output keystream generation loop:
     $i = (i+1) \bmod 256$  ;
     $j = (j + S[i]) \bmod 256$  ;
    swap ( $S[i], S[j]$ ) ;
     $t = (S[i] + S[j]) \bmod 256$  ;
    output  $Z = S[t]$  ;

```

Algorithm: RC4 PRGA

Graph 1:

Total number of distinct elements (keys) are 166 in output keystream bytes.

4. Proposed PRNG RC4-IP:

The proposed pseudorandom number generator (PRNG) known as RC4-IP is some modification of RC4 and NGG stream ciphers. The algorithm of RC4-IP is designed in two stages using two S-boxes S1 and S2. Like in the original RC4 first is KSA and the other is PRGA. In this algorithm two S-boxes S1 and S2 are used. In the first S-box S1 and the key array K, the multiplicative inverses of elemental polynomials under the irreducible polynomial $x^3 + 6x^2 + 4x + 1$ over $GF(7^3)$ are used and in the second S-box S2, the multiplicative inverses of elemental polynomials under the irreducible polynomial $x^3 + 4x + 1$ over $GF(7^3)$ are used. The elementary operations can be summarized as below.

Input: 1. Precomputed random array $a[0, 1, \dots, 255]$.

2. Precomputed random secret key array K.

Initialization:

for $i = 0, 1, \dots, 255$

$j = 0$;

$S1[i] = a_i$;

$T[i] = K[i \bmod \text{keylen}]$;

Scrambling:

for $i = 0, 1, \dots, 255$

$j = (S1[(j + S1[i] + T[i]) \bmod 256]) \bmod 256$;

swap ($S1[i], S1[j]$) ;

Algorithm: RC4-IP KSA

Input: 1. Key-dependent scrambled array $S1[0, 1, \dots, 255]$.

2. Precomputed random array $b[0, 1, \dots, 255]$.

Output: Pseudorandom keystream bytes Z .

Initialization:

$i = j = 0$;

Output keystream generation loop:

for $i = 0, 1, \dots, 255$;

$i = (i + 1) \bmod 256$;

$j = (j + S1[i]) \bmod 256$;

swap ($S2[i], S2[j]$) ;

$t = (S1[i] + S2[j]) \bmod 256$

output $Z = S[t]$;

Algorithm: RC4-IP PRGA

Graph2:

Total number of distinct elements (keys) are 169 in output keystream bytes.

5. Comparative Study of RC4 and RC4-IP by different Statistical Tests:

To present comparatively better results than previous, one has to develop a comparatively advance algorithm for higher p-values as p-values will be higher if the difference between the number of zeros and ones is minimize in the pseudorandom sequence. There are so many statistical tests for checking the p-values in different algorithms. Frequency test, Frequency test within a block, Runs test, and the test for Longest run of ones in a block are some important tests of them. These all tests determine the randomness of a binary sequence by accessing the number of zeros and ones. When they are approximately equal in number then it indicates the randomness output binary sequence.

The P-value is the probability of finding the observed results, under the null hypothesis of randomness, hence if the result of the P-value is less than 0.01 then the null hypothesis is accepted that means the cryptographic result is non-random. However, if the P-value is greater than or equal to 0.01 then the cryptographic result is random.

5.1 Frequency Test:

In frequency test, $p - value = erfc\left(\frac{S_{obs}}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$, where erfc is the complementary error function and

$$S_{obs} = \frac{|\#ones - \#zeros|}{\sqrt{n}}$$

The results of p-values for Frequency test of both the RC4 and the RC4-IP using the same input samples and keys are shown in Table 3.

Table-3 Frequency Test results

Samples	p-values		Success	
	RC4	RC4-IP	RC4	RC4-IP
1.	0.6877524392453405	0.764265268470139	True	True
2.	0.07520508329590504	0.7772682694962356	True	True
3.	0.5981126580705916	0.9938332263114685	True	True
4.	0.20829116093265446	0.3301301880045578	True	True
5.	0.01934631327235417	0.2953283492312877	True	True
6.	0.5852954781260322	0.9175119029076144	True	True
7.	0.16415972847851523	0.40911318756000337	False	True
8.	0.05868993162479902	0.09594814652671854	True	True
9.	0.2202677436618922	0.2670499825879775	True	True
10.	0.42329231771584236	0.7048957270050926	True	True

In Frequency Test, the p-values for the 10 samples of RC4 are represented in red colour, whereas of RC4-IP are represented in blue colour.

5.2 Frequency Test within a block:

In Frequency test within a block, $p\text{-value} = igamc\left(\frac{N}{2}, \frac{\chi^2(obs)}{2}\right)$, where $igamc$ is the incomplete gamma function, N is the number of non-overlapping blocks, and $\chi^2(obs)$ is a measure of how well the observed proportion of ones within a given M -bit block match the expected proportion(1/2).

The results of p-values for Frequency test within a block of both the RC4 and the RC4-IP using the same input samples and keys are shown in Table 4.

Table-4 Frequency test within a block results

Samples	p-values		Success	
	RC4	RC4-IP	RC4	RC4-IP
1.	0.05785704240499316	0.23783735601747086	True	True
2.	0.4310825850446039	0.6037248672154967	True	True
3.	0.015790357616016437	0.058193226399833126	True	True
4.	0.13812039831332645	0.30368647539966404	True	True
5.	0.3309300390926204	0.3990458109338806	True	True
6.	0.08453224177454624	0.8262244116147248	True	True
7.	0.1510393664067843	0.233939147860488	False	True
8.	0.16071491298171328	0.9524514722712208	True	True
9.	0.14967796610515563	0.6084160013556092	True	True
10.	0.13021933811174846	0.635066139622694	True	True

In Frequency Test within a block, the p-values for the 10 samples of RC4 are represented in green colour, whereas of RC4-IP are represented in purple colour.

5.3 Runs Test:

In Runs test, $p - value = erfc\left(\frac{|V_n(obs) - 2n\pi(1-\pi)|}{2\sqrt{2n\pi(1-\pi)}}\right)$, where $V_n(obs)$ is the total number of runs (that is the total number of zero runs + the total number of one-runs) across all n bits.

The results of p-values for Runs test within a block of both the RC4 and the RC4-IP using the same input samples and keys are shown in Table 5.

Table-5 Runs test results

Samples	p-values		Success	
	RC4	RC4-IP	RC4	RC4-IP
1.	0.22326438264211	0.26405664641560433	True	True
2.	0.00616734090069302	0.9714237502511169	True	True
3.	0.3054226826507731	0.7541489768343634	True	True
4.	0.39949645572278847	0.9797307295761155	True	True
5.	0.19678733351637706	0.31796670592995335	True	True
6.	0.09411624926170228	0.4675150384856972	True	True
7.	0.1417542572983537	0.3760313674784412	False	True
8.	0.1531775260893537	0.26192988827485664	True	True
9.	0.2536768060570871	0.546235447883314	True	True
10.	0.22323144583932808	0.939450916761282	True	True

In Run Test, the p-values for the 10 samples of RC4 are represented in red colour, whereas of RC4-IP are represented in blue colour.

5.4 Test for Longest run of ones in a block:

In the test for Longest run of ones in a block, $p - value = igamc\left(\frac{K}{2}, \frac{\chi^2(obs)}{2}\right)$, where K is the value

depending on the length of each block, and a measure of how well the observed longest run length within M-bit blocks matches the expected longest length within M-blocks.

The results of p-values for test for Longest run of ones in a block of both the RC4 and the RC4-IP using the same input samples and keys are shown in Table 6.

Table-6 Test results for the Longest-run of ones in a block.

Samples	p-values		Success	
	RC4	RC4-IP	RC4	RC4-IP
1.	0.06106345831293576	0.7527940997441357	True	True
2.	0.8842848389276898	0.9287306270041645	True	True
3.	0.39959546226545783	0.6212219879980128	True	True
4.	0.31056494134014845	0.8392985615580929	True	True
5.	0.023101765702467452	0.9145100890260512	True	True
6.	0.9737444504885402	0.9936235018804211	True	True
7.	0.6212219879980128	0.8768790942601203	False	True
8.	0.026216654236214075	0.41681323066584597	True	True
9.	0.24891850549210542	0.39079498389182293	True	True
10.	0.06572843386611346	0.4121220150540892	True	True

In Test for Longest Run of Ones in a Block, the p-values for the 10 samples of RC4 are represented in green colour, whereas of RC4-IP are represented in purple colour.

6. Conclusion:

The present study is an advanced version of RC4. In section 2 of this manuscript, Extended Euclidean Algorithm has been discussed for computing multiplicative inverses of elemental polynomials over $GF(7^3)$. In Table1 and Table2 we have collected the multiplicative inverses of 342 elemental polynomials of $GF(7^3)$ with respect to the irreducible polynomials $x^3 + 6x^2 + 4x + 1$ and $x^3 + 4x + 1$ respectively. In section 3, we have used our key in RC4 algorithm 166 distinct output keystream bytes which are shown in Graph1, and in section 4, we have designed a new PRNG RC4-IP in which the multiplicative inverses of Table1 and Table2 are used in S-box and K-box (keys) and found 169 distinct output keystream bytes which is shown in Graph 2. The comparative study of Graph 1 and Graph 2 indicates that the RC4-IP is more uniform than the RC4 algorithm. In section 5, we have used different four statistical tests for computing p-values. Based on these test results shown in Table3, Table4, Table5, and Table6, all the encrypted texts for both the RC4 and the RC4-IP are random since the computed p-values are higher than 0.01. The comparative study of p-values in all the tests shows that the distribution of ones and zeros has improved in the RC4-IP over the RC4. Hence, the RC4-IP is better than the RC4 in terms of computed p-values.

7. Acknowledgements:

We express our gratitude to Md. Qamar Talib Sahab for his suggestions and arrangement of books. We are also thankful to Prof. Ranjana, Head of the University Department of Mathematics, TMBU, Bhagalpur, for providing her moral support and guidance. We express my heartiest gratitude to Sandip Suman, Assistant Professor, University Department of Mathematics, TMBU, Bhagalpur, for helping in coding. We would like to express my gratitude to the Variant Research Centre for providing necessary facilities towards research activities.

8. References:

1. Stallings, W., "Finite Fields," in Cryptography and Network Security Principles and Practices, 4th ed., Delhi, Pearson Education, 95-133(2008).
2. Forouzan, B.A., Mukhopadhyay, D., "Mathematics of Cryptography," in Cryptography and Network Security, 2nd ed., New Delhi, TMH, 15-43 (2011).
3. Knuth, D.E.: The Art of Computer Programming Seminumerical Algorithms, 3rd edn, vol. 2. Pearson Education, Upper Saddle River (2011).
4. Church R., "Tables of Irreducible Polynomials for the first four Prime Moduli", Annals of Mathematics, Vol. 36(1), pp. 198-209, January, 1935.
5. Paul, G., Maitra, S., "RC4 Stream Cipher and its Variants," Boca Raton, Chapman & Hall/CRC (2012).
6. Stinson, D.R., "The RSA Cryptosystem and Factoring Integers," in Cryptography Theory and Practice, 3rd ed., Boca Raton: Chapman & Hall/CRC, 161-232 (2006).
7. Rudolf Lidl, "Introduction to finite fields and their applications, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, London New York.
8. J K M Sadique Uz Zaman, "A Pseudorandom Number Generator using Irreducible Polynomial over $GF(7^3)$.", Journal of Theoretical Physics & Cryptography, IJPC, Vol. 12, December 2016.

9. Suman Das, Indian Academy of Sciences, Sadhana (2019)44:223 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12046-019-1209-7>.
10. Santanu Sarkar, Revisiting Roos Bias in RC4 Key Scheduling Algorithm, HAL open science, HAL Id: hal-01275377 <https://hal.inria.fr/hal-01275377>.
11. Maytham Hammood, RC4 stream cipher with two state tables, Lecture notes in Electrical Engineering, January 2013.
12. Poonam Jindal, A survey on RC4 Stream Cipher , International Journal of Computer Network and Information security, June 2015.
13. F Akbar, Comparative analysis of RC4+ algorithm, RC4 NGG algorithm and RC4 GGHN algorithm on image file security, Material Science and Engineering 420 (2018) 012131.
14. Isnar Sumartono, An Overview of the RC4 Algorithm, IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences, December 2016.
15. Poonam Jindal, Optimization of the Security-Performance Tradeoff in RC4 Encryption Algorithm, Wireless Personal Communications, February 2017.
16. Matthew E. McKague, Design and Analysis of RC4-like Stream Ciphers, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada, 2005.
17. Dilshad Akhtar, M.R. Hassan, Neda Fatma, “Incorporating a new Pseudorandom number Generator in AES Algorithm to Improve its security level” The Ciência & Engenharia - Science & Engineering Journal ISSN: 0103-944X Volume 11 Issue 1, 2023 pp: 1825 – 1840. <https://seer-ufu-br.online/index.php/journal/issue/view/3>
18. Dilshad Akhtar, M.R. Hassan, Neda Fatma, J.K.M. Sadique Uz zaman, “Computation of Multiplicative Inverses of non-zero Polynomials of GF(73) by Gauss-Jordan Method” The Ciência & Engenharia - Science & Engineering Journal ISSN: 0103-944X Volume 11 Issue 1, 2023 pp: 1183 – 1198. <https://seer-ufu-br.online/index.php/journal/article/view/267>